

**ASSESSMENT OF THE LEVEL OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT OF
PRESCHOOL CHILDREN IN THE CITY OF FERGANA USING INDICES****Sidikova Gulbahor Sabirovna¹, Tychiev Ashurali Ibragimovich²**¹⁻²Teachers of Ferghana State University

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Annotation: The article is based on the physical development of children using various indices.

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Physical development (PD) of a growing organism is the main indicator of a child's health. The greater the deviations in physical development, the higher the likelihood of diseases. Simplicity, availability of methods for studying PD and high information content of the data obtained give the indicators of PD the value of an objective criterion for the well-being of the child population and find their place in the characterization of the regional environmental and hygienic situation [9]. Drawing up standards for the physical development of children and their periodic updating can be examples of environmental monitoring, which consists in monitoring changes in the processes of people's life activity in connection with the impact of external factors on them.

To characterize the RF, three main anthropometric indicators are informative: body weight, body length, chest circumference [3, 5]. Recently, the index method has been used to assess the RF of children, although, as a rule, it is used as an additional technique [3]. Indices are ratios of individual anthropometric features expressed in mathematical formulas. Different indices include a different number of features. The simplest indices include two features: weight-height and chest-height indicators. Weight and height include body mass index (BMI) and Rohrer index [1]. For chest-weight - the index of Pignet, Brugsch and Verweck.

Comparative analysis of the assessment of the physical development of preschool children aged 3–6 years using the method of indices and centile tables. We examined 189 children aged 3 to 6 attending kindergarten No. 5. Obtaining parental informed consent to participate in the study was a mandatory procedure when children were included in one of the groups. The main anthropometric indicators were measured in preschoolers: body weight (kg), body length (cm), chest circumference (cm). The assessment of the

harmony of the physical development of children was carried out using the "Interregional standards for assessing the length and weight of the body of children from 0 to 14 years" [4]. Depending on the ratio of body length and weight, the children were divided into three groups: the 1st group consisted of 153 children with harmonious FR, the 2nd group - 10 children with disharmonious FR due to body weight deficiency, the 3rd group - 26 children with disharmonious RF due to excess body weight.

Further, according to the harmony groups, the level of physical development of preschoolers was calculated using calculated indices that take into account body weight (BW, kg), body length (BL, cm), chest circumference (BCC, cm) of the child. To assess the RF of children, the Quetelet index or body mass index (BMI) = BW/BL^2 (kg/m²) was used [1, 2, 8]; Pinier index = $DT - (MT + WGC)$ (units) [1, 6, 8]; Rohrer index = MT/DT^3 (kg/m³) [1, 2, 8]; Brugsch index = $WGC \times 100/DT$ (%) [1, 8]; Verweck index = $DT/2MT + WGC$ (units) [2, 3].

Various methods of parametric statistics (calculation of the M-weighted arithmetic mean, mean error (m), standard deviation (σ), significance of differences in mean values by Student's t-test and Fisher's F-test).

The distribution of preschoolers into groups with different levels of RF (corresponding to body length and weight according to interregional standards) is shown in Table 1. The results of the studies revealed that the largest number of children belonged to the group with harmonious RF (Group 1) (81%). Deviations of morphometric parameters from the norm were found in 19% of children. Moreover, among children with disharmonious RF, preschoolers with overweight (14%) (Group 3) were more common in relation to the indicators of the 2nd group - with underweight (5%). A comparative analysis of the characteristics of the physical development of children examined by the centile method showed that the body weight of preschoolers with harmonious physical development (18.80 ± 2.98 kg) is significantly higher than the body weight of children with disharmonious development due to its deficiency (16.11 ± 3.65 kg) by an average of 2.69 kg. According to such indicators as body length and chest circumference, there were no significant differences in the characteristics of the compared groups. Children with overweight (23.46 ± 3.87 kg) with a high degree of reliability ($p < 0.000$) exceeded the characteristics of preschool children with harmonious risk factors (18.02 ± 2.98 kg) in this indicator. In addition, they had significantly larger chest circumference (60.81 ± 4.28 cm) than the children of the 1st group (55.94 ± 2.81 cm).

The characteristics of the physical development of preschoolers, identified with the help of calculated height-weight indices, is presented in table 2.

Assessment of the RF of preschool children aged 3–6 using the Quetelet index (BMI) showed significant differences among children with different levels of harmonicity of the RF

($p < 0.05$). The greatest deviation from the recommended values for the studied age was observed in children of the 3rd group with overweight.

The calculation of the Pignet index in preschoolers revealed a significant difference between children with harmonious RF (37.04 ± 10.73 units) and those with higher body weights (28.77 ± 3.50 units) ($p < 0.000$). The index characterizes the type of physique and the lower its index, the stronger the child's physique. For the Pinier index, values from 10 to 25 units are recommended. The level of the Pinier index of the surveyed preschool children in Irkutsk in all the studied groups indicated a weak and very weak type of their physique.

The Rohrer index is a group indicator of dolicho and brachymorphy, and ecologists explain the nature of these features by adaptation to the geographic and climatic conditions of residence of various populations. The values of the Rohrer index of children, which according to centile tables are characterized as harmonious and disharmonious due to underweight, were 14.01 ± 1.33 and 12.05 ± 1.36 kg/m³, respectively, which corresponds to the recommended characteristics (10, 7–13.7 kg/m³) (Table 2). Whereas the values of this index in children with disharmonious RF due to overweight (16.18 ± 1.11 kg/m³) exceeded them. All differences in the characteristics of the indices in the compared groups are highly significant ($p < 0.000$).

The values of the Brugsch index in preschool children with harmonious PR were $50.95 \pm 2.61\%$, with disharmonious PR due to underweight - $50.08 \pm 3.50\%$, with disharmonious PR due to overweight - $53.84 \pm 2.48\%$. The revealed characteristics of the Brugsch index testified to the narrow chest of all preschool children, which did not contradict the definition of their body type according to the level of the Pinier index as weak and very weak. According to the values of the Verweck index, there are three types of physique: mesomorphic – medium Characteristics of indicators of physical development groups of preschoolers aged 3–6 years ($X \pm \sigma$)

Note. * - Student's coefficient ($p \geq 0.05$); # - Fisher coefficient ($p \geq 0.05$) in relation to the 1st group.

Body size variant, brachymorphic - wide body and short limbs; dolichomorphic

- narrow body and long limbs [2, 3]. The results of the analysis of the Verweck index showed that the somatotype of children in the 1st group (1.18 ± 0.05 units) and the 3rd group (1.05 ± 0.05 units) can be attributed to the mesomorphic type (1.25–0.85), while preschool children of the 2nd group with a body weight deficit (1.27 ± 0.04 units) were characterized by moderate dolichomorpha (1.35–1.25). Children with moderate brachymorphy (0.85–0.75) and severe brachymorphy (< 0.75) were not identified in the study. Thus, the calculation of various height-weight indices for the surveyed preschoolers aged 3–6 years in Irkutsk, taking into account the preliminary assessment of the harmony of their physical development, showed that such indices as Quetelet, Rohrer and Verweck in the surveyed preschoolers corresponded to the harmonicity groups of the RF, which were determined using the method of centile tables. However, the values of the Pignet and Brugsch index of all preschoolers differed from the characteristics proposed by various authors as normative ones [1, 5, 8] and indicated a weak physique of the examined children, including the overweight group. This discrepancy may be due to the fact that the morphometric characteristics of the child population undergo significant changes over a long period of time and require periodic adjustment of their assessment.

Characteristics of indicators of physical development groups of preschoolers aged 3–6 years ($X \pm \sigma$)

Note. * - Student's coefficient ($p \leq 0.05$); # - Fisher coefficient ($p \leq 0.05$) in relation to the 1st group.

Table 1

Indicators Group	1 (n = 153)	Group 2 (n = 10)	Group 3 (n = 26)
Body weight, kg	18.80 ± 2.98	$16.11 \pm 3.65^{**}$	23.46 ± 3.87
Body length, cm	110.31 ± 8.07	110.05 ± 11.53	113.04 ± 7.56

Body size variant, brachymorphic - wide body and short limbs; dolichomorphic - narrow body and long limbs [2, 3]. The results of the analysis of the Verweck index showed that the somatotype of children in the 1st group (1.18 ± 0.05 units) and the 3rd group (1.05 ± 0.05 units) can be attributed to the mesomorphic type (1.25–0.85), while preschool children of the 2nd group with a body weight deficit (1.27 ± 0.04 units) were characterized by moderate dolichomorpha (1.35–1.25). Children with moderate brachymorphy (0.85–0.75) and severe brachymorphy (< 0.75) were not identified in the study. Thus, the calculation of various height-weight indices for the surveyed preschoolers aged 3–6 years in Irkutsk, taking into account the preliminary assessment of the

harmony of their physical development, showed that such indices as Quetelet, Rohrer and Verweck in the surveyed preschoolers corresponded to the harmonicity groups of the RF, which were determined using the method of centile tables. However, the values of the Pignet and Brugsch index of all preschoolers differed from the characteristics proposed by various authors as normative ones [1, 5, 8] and indicated a weak physique of the examined children, including the overweight group. This discrepancy may be due to the fact that the morphometric characteristics of the child population undergo significant changes over a long period of time and require periodic adjustment of their assessment.

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